

MODELING OF FRACTURE OF WHISKER REINFORCED CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a theoretical investigation of the critical strain energy release rate, G_c , of whisker reinforced ceramic matrix composites. Crack deflection and whisker pull-out are considered as the major energy dissipation mechanism in fracture. The modeling of crack deflection is conducted based on a determination of the path of advancement of the deflected crack front along whiskers. The knowledge of crack path provides the basis for evaluating the deflection-induced reduction in strain energy release rate. Whisker pull-out is analyzed in terms of the work done against sliding friction in extracting whiskers from the broken matrix. The theoretical predictions are compared with experimental data of SiC whisker reinforced Al_2O_3 composites.

INTRODUCTION

Ceramic matrix composites have been the focus of substantial research effort in recent years. The major driving force for ceramic matrix composite development is the potential of utilizing ceramics with greater thermal and mechanical reliability. A feasible approach for improving mechanical reliability is through the enhancement of fracture toughness.¹

The mechanisms of failure in whisker reinforced ceramics are very different from those in monolithic ceramics, which often fail by the growth of a single major crack on a plane normal to the maximum principal stress. Whisker composites, on the other hand, can fail by a variety of mechanisms, depending on the whisker/matrix interfacial characteristic and the interaction between a crack front and the reinforcements. For the SiC_w/Al₂O₃ composites, crack deflection and a small amount of whisker pull-out were observed on fracture surfaces.²

Fig. 1 Schematic view of hot-pressed sample.

Furthermore, because of the large aspect ratio of whiskers, specimens produced by hot-pressing tend to orient the whiskers in a random manner in planes perpendicular to the hot-pressing axis, as shown in Fig.1. The fracture mechanisms in different crack propagation directions relative to the fiber orientation (Fig.1) are different. In this paper, a comprehensive treatment of the failure mechanism and fracture toughness based upon the three different types of crack propagation (A, B and C) in Fig. 1 is given. The

analytical predictions are compared with experimental work on SiC whisker reinforced Al₂O₃. The enhancement in critical strain energy release rate will be examined by considering the effects of orientation, volume fraction, aspect ratio, pull-out angle of whiskers and the whisker/matrix interfacial strength.

ANALYSIS OF CRACK DEFLECTION

The enhancement in fracture toughness due to crack deflection can be evaluated based upon the knowledge of the stress intensity factors K_1 , K_2 and K_3 , corresponding to the tilt angle θ and twist angle ϕ . The extension of the crack is then governed by the strain energy release rate, G , along its deflected trajectory

$$G = \frac{K_1^2(1-\nu^2) + K_2^2(1-\nu^2) + K_3^2(1+\nu)}{E} \quad (1)$$

Here, E and ν are, respectively, the Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of the material.

The increase in fracture toughness due to crack deflection in a composite material is evaluated from the stress intensity of the tilted or twisted crack front. Then, the critical strain energy release rate, G_c , is obtained by considering the ratio of the strain energy release rates of the undeflected (G^m) and deflected ($\langle G \rangle^d$) cracks³

$$G_c = (G^m / \langle G \rangle^d) G_c^m \quad (2)$$

where G_c^m is the critical strain energy release rate of an undeflected crack, and $\langle G \rangle^d$ is the average value for all the possible deflected configurations.

For the purpose of illustration, we consider the interaction of a crack front (line P_0Q_0 in Fig. 2) with two adjacent whiskers oriented at angles θ_1 , θ_2 , μ_1 and μ_2 with respect to the main crack surface. Also in Fig. 2, θ_1 and θ_2 are of the same sign; the deflection of the crack surface along the fibers results in a "tilted" crack.

In order to define the morphology of the tilted crack surface in Fig. 2, the two whisker segments protruding the main crack plane are divided into M segments. Let α and β denote the lengths of the two segments; the divisions on the two segments are of lengths α/M and β/M .

Fig. 2 Schematic view of like-sign deflection.

Fig. 3 Schematic view of opposite-sign deflection.

The extension of the crack front from its initial location of P_0Q_0 in Fig. 2 is discussed in the following. Although crack extension along the whiskers is believed to be a continuous process, we focus on the crack front locations at $P_0, P_1, \dots, P_{i-1}, \dots, P_M$ along the whisker of length α , and the locations at $Q_0, Q_1, \dots, Q_j, \dots, Q_M$ along the whisker of length β , for the convenience of numerical calculations. Now consider an instantaneous location of the crack front at P_iQ_j . The subsequent crack front location, according to the divisions made on the whisker segments could be $P_iQ_{j+1}, P_{i+1}Q_j$ or $P_{i+1}Q_{j+1}$. The strain energy release rates corresponding to these three paths of crack extensions are calculated and the new crack front location associated with the maximum strain energy release rate⁴ is identified. Assume that crack extension takes place and the front assumes the new position of P_iQ_{j+1} . Then the calculation process for G is repeated for the locations of $P_iQ_{j+2}, P_{i+1}Q_{j+1}$ and $P_{i+1}Q_{j+2}$.

This process continues until the crack front reaches the end of one of the whiskers. It is assumed then that the extension of the deflected crack becomes unstable, and the maximum critical strain energy release rate is obtained. By integrating over all the possible relative positions of the two whiskers of identical length, L , (i.e., lengths α and β , and orientation angles $\theta_1, \theta_2, \mu_1$ and μ_2), the average strain energy release rate is expressed in the general form as

$$\frac{\langle G \rangle^t}{G^m} = \frac{4}{L^2 \pi^4} \int_0^L \int_0^L \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} \int_0^{\pi/2} \int_0^{\pi/2} \frac{\left[\Delta - \left(\frac{I}{M} \alpha \cos \theta_1 \sin \mu_1 - \frac{J}{M} \beta \cos \theta_2 \sin \mu_2 \right) \right]}{\left[(\Delta'_{(I,J)})^2 + \left(\frac{I}{M} \alpha \sin \theta_1 - \frac{J}{M} \beta \sin \theta_2 \right)^2 \right]^{1/2}} \cdot \cos^4 \left(\frac{\langle \theta \rangle_{P_i Q_j}}{2} \right) d\theta_1 d\theta_2 d\mu_1 d\mu_2 d\alpha d\beta \quad (3)$$

Either I or J is equal to M in Eq. (3). The expression inside the integral signs of Eq.(3) is the strain energy release rate of a crack with the front line reaching one of the two adjacent whisker ends. The above calculation is repeated for all the possible whisker configurations.

Consider the schematic view of whisker-crack configuration in Fig. 3. The line P_0Q_0 again denotes the undeflected crack front. The whisker angular positions θ_1 and θ_2 are of opposite signs and the interaction of the main crack with the whiskers gives rise to a "twisted" crack surface. The path of the twisted crack is identified by the same method as that for tilted crack. Integrating over all possible whisker configurations, the average strain energy release rate due to twisting of crack front can be written as

$$\frac{\langle G \rangle^T}{G^m} = \frac{4}{L^2 \pi^4} \int_0^L \int_0^L \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} \int_0^{\pi/2} \int_0^{\pi/2} \frac{\left[\Delta - \left(\frac{I}{M} \alpha \cos \theta_1 \sin \mu_1 - \frac{J}{M} \beta \cos \theta_2 \sin \mu_2 \right) \right]}{\left[(\Delta'_{(I,J)})^2 + \left(\frac{I}{M} \alpha \sin \theta_1 - \frac{J}{M} \beta \sin \theta_2 \right)^2 \right]^{1/2}} \left[\cos^4 \langle \lambda \rangle_{(I,J)/2} \right] \cdot \{ 2v \sin^2 \phi_{(I,J)} + \cos^2 \phi_{(I,J)} \cos^2 \langle \lambda \rangle_{(I,J)/2} [1 + 2 \sin^2 \langle \lambda \rangle_{(I,J)/2}] \}^2 + \{ \sin \phi_{(I,J)} \cos \phi_{(I,J)} [\cos^2 \langle \lambda \rangle_{(I,J)/2} - 2v] + \sin^2 \langle \lambda \rangle_{(I,J)/2} [3 \cos^2 \langle \lambda \rangle_{(I,J)/2} - 2v] \}^2 d\theta_1 d\theta_2 d\mu_1 d\mu_2 d\alpha d\beta \quad (4)$$

where either I or J is equal to M . The total average strain energy release rate due to crack deflection is

$$\langle G \rangle^d = \frac{\langle G \rangle^t}{2} + \frac{\langle G \rangle^T}{2} \quad (5)$$

ANALYSIS OF WHISKER PULL-OUT

Consider the interaction of an advancing crack with whiskers as shown in Fig. 4, in which only whisker pull-out is shown. It is assumed here that the shear stress τ_i is constant throughout this process. The total work done for whisker pull-out per unit area of a specimen cross-section is

$$G_c^p = \frac{V_{pf}}{\pi r^2} \left(\frac{l_c}{L} \right) \int_0^{l_c/2} \pi r \tau_i x^2 \frac{dx}{l_c/2} = \frac{V_{pf}}{12} \left(\frac{l_c}{L} \right) \sigma_w^* l_c \quad (6)$$

where V_{pf} , r and L are the volume fraction of pull-out whiskers, whisker radius and the average length of whiskers, respectively. The critical whisker pull-out length, l_c , is defined as the whisker length from the fracture plane for which the axial tensile stress reaches the fracture strength, σ_w^* , i.e.

$$l_c = \sigma_w^* r / \tau_i \quad (7)$$

Thus, the relative critical strain energy release rate due to the work of whisker pull-out is given by

$$\frac{G_c^p}{G_c^m} = \frac{E_m V_{pf}}{12(K_c^m)^2 (1 - \nu_m^2)} \left(\frac{l_c}{L}\right) \sigma_w^* l_c \quad (8)$$

where E_m , ν_m and K_c^m are, respectively, the matrix Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio and fracture toughness.

Fig. 4 Schematic drawing of a crack interacting with the whiskers.

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND COMPARISONS WITH EXPERIMENTS

For the crack propagation direction of plane A (Fig. 1), the crack plane is essentially parallel to the "plane" containing the whisker axes. However, it should be recognized that the whiskers are not absolutely perpendicular to the hot-pressing axis. Thus, there is some of misalignment between the whisker axes and the plane A. The maximum misalignment is denoted by the angle ζ (Fig. 5), and it also represents the maximum deflection angle of the crack plane by the whiskers. Since no whisker is aligned parallel to the applied tensile stress in the z-direction, the amount of whisker pull-out is expected to be zero. It means that the toughening mechanism in plane A is only due to small angle crack deflection, and the relative strain energy release rate can be calculated by setting the deflection angles θ_1 and θ_2 from 0 to ζ in Eqs.(3) and (4).

Fig. 5 Schematic view of whisker orientation in plane A.⁵

Fig. 6 Relative G_c predictions of plane A type crack as a function of misalignment angle, ζ .⁵

The relative critical strain energy release rate obtained from Eqs.(3), (4) and (2) by numerical integration as a function of misalignment angle ζ at 20% whisker volume fraction is presented in Fig. 6.⁵ A comparison of the analytical results with the experimental data of Becher and Wei⁶ concludes that the misalignment angle is about 10 degrees.

For the situation depicted in Fig. 1, the crack plane B is normal to the "plane" containing the whisker axis but it is normal to the longitudinal axes of only a small portion of the whiskers. Thus, the amount of whiskers pulled out is expected to be small. Unless the whisker axes are aligned nearly parallel to the applied tensile stress in the y-direction, the whiskers will cause the crack to deflect rather than being pulled out. In the present analysis, it is assumed that a whisker whose axis is within the critical pull-out angle β_c and with its end lying within $l_c/2$ from the crack plane will have a pull-out effect (Fig. 7). The volume fraction of pulled-out whiskers, V_{pf} , is given by

$$V_{pf} = \frac{1 - \cos\beta_c}{2\sin\zeta} V_f \quad (\zeta \geq \beta_c); \quad V_{pf} = \frac{\pi(1 - \cos\zeta) + 2\zeta(\beta_c - \zeta)}{2\pi\sin\zeta} V_f \quad (\zeta \leq \beta_c) \quad (9)$$

The resultant critical strain energy release rate of the combined mechanisms in plane B is given by

$$G_c = G_c^d + G_c^p \quad (10)$$

The range of integration for $\langle G \rangle^t$ in Eq.(3) is

$$\frac{1}{4L^2\zeta^2} \int_0^L \int_0^L \int_{-\zeta}^{\zeta} \int_{-\zeta}^{\zeta} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\beta_c - |\mu_2|}} \int_0^{\pi/2 - \sqrt{\beta_c - |\mu_2|}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\beta_c - |\mu_1|}} \left\{ \dots \right\} d\theta_1 d\theta_2 d\mu_1 d\mu_2 d\alpha d\beta \quad (11)$$

where $\sqrt{\beta_c - |\mu_1|}$ and $\sqrt{\beta_c - |\mu_2|}$ are equal to zero if the quantities inside the symbol " $\sqrt{\quad}$ " are negative. Similarly, $\langle G \rangle^T$ for a twisted crack in Eq. (4) can be obtained by using the θ_2 range from $-\pi/2 + \sqrt{\beta_c - |\mu_2|}$ to 0. G_c^p is given by Eq.(8). The calculated resultant critical strain energy release rate is compared with the experimental results of Becher, Tiegs, Ogle, and Warwick² and presented in Fig. 8 for three critical angles. The analytical prediction of critical pull-out angle β_c is about 10 degree.

Fig. 7 Schematic view of whisker orientation in plane B.

Fig. 8 Relative G_c predictions of plane B type crack as a function of volume fraction.

For the situation depicted in Fig. 1, the crack plane C is normal to the "plane" containing the whisker axis but it is normal to the longitudinal axes of only a small portion of the whiskers. Thus, the amount of whiskers pulled out in plane C is the same as those in plane B. But the crack deflection in plane C is different from that in plane B (Fig. 9). The range of integration for $\langle G \rangle^t$ in Eq.(3) in plane C is

$$\frac{1}{2L^2\zeta^2} \int_0^L \int_0^L \int_{\pi/2 - \zeta}^{\pi/2} \int_{\pi/2 - \zeta}^{\pi/2} \frac{1}{\pi/2 - \sqrt{\beta_c - |\pi/2 - \theta_2|}} \int_{-\pi/2}^{-\sqrt{\beta_c - |\pi/2 - \theta_2|}} \frac{1}{\pi/2 - \sqrt{\beta_c - |\pi/2 - \theta_1|}} \int_{-\pi/2}^{-\sqrt{\beta_c - |\pi/2 - \theta_1|}} \left\{ \dots \right\} d\mu_1 d\mu_2 d\theta_1 d\theta_2 d\alpha d\beta \quad (12)$$

where $|\beta_c - |\pi/2 - \theta_1||$ and $|\beta_c - |\pi/2 - \theta_2||$ are equal to zero as the quantities inside the symbol " \backslash " are negative. Similarly, $\langle G \rangle^T$ for a twisted crack in Eq.(4) can be obtained by using the θ_2 range from $-\pi/2$ to $-\pi/2 + \zeta$. The calculated resultant critical strain energy release rate at misalignment angle of 10 degree and critical pull-out angle $\beta_c = 10$ degree is compared with the experimental results of Boulanger, Chiang, Majidi and Chou⁷ and presented in Fig.10.

Fig. 9 Schematic view of whisker orientation in plane C.

Fig. 10 Relative G_c predictions of plane C type crack as a function of volume fraction.

CONCLUSION

A. A theoretical modeling work has been conducted for the fracture toughness of whisker reinforced ceramic matrix composites. Results show that the critical strain energy release rates of cracks in specimens prepared by hot-pressing are very sensitive to the crack orientation.

B. Due to two-dimensional texture of whisker reinforced ceramic matrix composites, cracks of different propagation directions have different fracture mechanisms. The toughening mechanism of A plane (Fig. 1) is low angle crack deflection. In B plane the toughening is due to crack deflection with large angle range and a small amount of whisker pull-out. The crack with C propagation direction has the toughening mechanisms of high angle and short range crack deflection as well as the same amount of whisker pull-out as plane B. The theoretical predictions of the critical strain energy release rates for three different crack propagation directions are consistent with the experimental results. These conclusions are also supported by the experimental observations of fracture surfaces in SiC whisker reinforced alumina by Wei and Becher.⁸

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